

THE 'INTERIOR SCHWARZSCHILD PROBLEM'; EXACT EQUATIONS AND TESTS OF CONSISTENCY

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ABSTRACT

The exact equations for energy-density and metric inside a non-rotating sphere of perfect fluid derived in a previous paper by the author are presented here in summarized fashion. It is proved that the equations are fully consistent with four exact relations known from general relativity theory. Three of these exact relations are associated with the names of Tolman, Oppenheimer, Volkoff and S. Weinberg. The fourth test concerns the trace of the energy-momentum tensor, which in general relativity must be proportional to the Ricci scalar.

Key words: perfect fluid sphere, energy density, metric, consistency with known exact identities